

Entrepreneurship can be Driven and Inculcated – a Case study on Technical and Business Communication Skills as an open Elective Course

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Abstract:

The myths have been shattered that engineers can only create technology and not build enterprises. It is proven that engineers can become great entrepreneurs. This is because they have the technical knowledge and the required skills developed over the years to handle several projects and critical issues.

The Choice-Based Credit System is widely practiced by many institutions in India since it has become a signatory of the University Grants Commission. This has been promoted in such a way that different open elective courses should be offered by every department in engineering to other departments. This interdisciplinary of learning open elective courses by other department students, especially in engineering education will have learning awareness and job-oriented benefits.

Engineering students have an opportunity to choose any open elective course from different departments and apply their knowledge to acquire jobs in that field of course. Learning, and employment benefits are not only through their course subjects but also through open elective courses.

In this paper an attempt is made to analyze the various factors affecting the choice of an open elective by the students, to enhance teaching, learning, and employment opportunities. In the present case study, the subject Technical and Business Communication offered by the Department of English at our university to the students of other branches was taken as a reference. It was observed that most of the CSE Students have shown enormous interest in choosing this subject for various reasons. All these factors associated with the selection of this subject by computer science students are carefully evaluated and analyzed through a qualitative and quantitative approach.

Keywords: *Open Elective, Technical and Business Communication, choice-based credit system, university grants commission.*

Introduction

University Grants Commission has come up with the Choice-Based Credit System (CBCS) in which the students have the option to select from the prescribed courses, which are referred to as core, elective, minor or soft skill courses and they can learn at their own pace and the entire assessment is grade-based on a credit system. The basic idea is to look into the needs of the students to keep up-to-date with the development of higher education in India and abroad. CBCS aims to redefine the curriculum keeping pace with the liberalization and globalization in education. The advantages of Choice Based Credit System particularly in open electives are as follows.

The CBCS offers a 'cafeteria' approach in which learn at their own pace of interest. They can also opt for an interdisciplinary approach to learning a subject. Students can choose open elective courses of their own choice. They can have more scope to enhance their skills and more scope of taking up case studies, projects, assignments, and vocational training including entrepreneurship. The system improves the job opportunities of students. The system will help in enabling potential employers to assess the performance of students on a scientific scale. One of the positives of selecting an interdisciplinary course from the huge number of open electives, you may choose in any field, as long as you may not meet the prerequisites. This advantage allows you to go broad, and add a third concentration go deep, and take more open elective courses in either concentration, or go forward and use all those concepts in the real field.

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Methodology

Open Elective is a powerful tool introduced in the third year second semester of the School of Engineering, Anurag University syllabus which allows a student to design the syllabus of a subject of his own choice which was offered by other departments and then students can then opt for this subject as an open Elective subject (i.e., OE- II). With the concept of Open Electives, a student can select new subjects from other streams or subjects from the same stream which were not initially available in the mainstream curriculum, after due approval from the Board of Studies followed by ratification by the Academic Council. The Open elective can be of great value to all students if properly utilized. Suppose from all the given options for open Elective, you don't find any subject of good use to you or if all the given subjects are of hardly any interest to you from your department, then you can select a course from another department, which helps your career. Now, this makes the deal more lucrative. Students are allowed to study a subject of their choice and their own designed syllabus. Suppose some of the students have finally decided to opt for an Open Elective course in Technical and Business Communication.

Description of Case study

Every Student is owed with username and password that he can access for all open elective courses offered by all departments. He alone can choose his own interesting open elective course to make the most of the student degree program, it is important to complete course requirements in all aspects. Our university curriculum blends both core and non-core courses that are focused on the student degree program and opted for Technical and Business Communication courses to expand on student interests to become entrepreneurs. Core courses include subjects that teach necessary and valuable information that are directly related to his field of study. But Technical and Business Communication would provide him with the knowledge to take up entrepreneurship. Many students assume that entrepreneurship is only meant for business administration students. During teachers' presentations on open elective courses especially Technical and Business communication skills objectives were clearly explained. Technical and Business Communication classes provide students with practical applications of Technical and Business Communication skills. They could even just satisfy their curiosity about knowing the present trend of Startup culture. Nearly 400 students opted for this course as their open elective.

Results and observations from student's feedback

Observations made from this Technical and Business Communication course which was first introduced and opted by computer science students as an open elective. Since a student cannot go through different aspects of Technical and Business Communication, Subject teachers' involvement would be very much useful in delivering the course perfectly and satisfying the course objective and outcome. Each student is viewed as a beneficiary and ready to become an entrepreneur or willing to take up parents' business with new ideas and energy.

The following feedback form was given to the students to assess the benefits of this course from the student's perspective. The feedback questions were framed to assess the utility to the student, the role of the teacher, and whether the students want to continue opting for such kinds of courses in the future for the benefit of knowledge sharing with other students, and getting aware of start-up culture and entrepreneurship.

The critical evaluation was done in improving the standards of open elective courses which is a part of the choice-based system. The achievement of the objectives of the task was assessed from the feedback

forms. A total of 70 student respondents answered the questionnaire. The ratings and the reference drawn are tabulated in Table 2.

Conclusion

From the analysis of the questionnaire survey and general observation of overall course interaction, the following conclusions were made.

- About 60% of pre-final year students exercised the option to have Technical and Business communication skills as their open elective.
- It is interesting to note that all of them are CSE students who have no prior idea of entrepreneurship and start-ups.
- It was understood from students' interactions that they have understood the three categories of benefits namely creating jobs instead of looking for a job, clear awareness of how to establish a start-up, and making up their minds to do a master's program in Management Science.
- It was felt by students that their employability potential significantly improved after studying this course.
- Students think that some of them can become very good entrepreneurs with the knowledge gained from this course.
- Student's commitment toward responsibility to society was considerably improved as an outcome of this course.
- Students are showing interest to work in teams instead of alone and also noticed a lot of discussion among the peer group.

Table 1

Feedback form for self –Study Rating: Yes/No

S. No	Questions	Rating
1.	Are you given a choice to select your open elective on your own?	
2.	Do you think this TBCS subject initiated you into self-learning?	
3.	Did you find sufficient material to study?	
4.	Did this course help you in looking at different start-up opportunities?	
5.	Did this course enhance your usage of tools for your employment?	

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6.	Do you think it enhanced your communication skills?	
7.	Did the course help you to get aware of the latest trends?	
8.	Were you able to implement the knowledge gained from this course in your real field?	
9.	Do you think the course teacher is capable of dealing with this subject?	
10.	Do you think self-study should be better than the lecturer taught?	
11.	Do you think that you are responsible for your career planning and execution?	

Table 2: Critical evaluation of student feedback

Q No	Rating	%	Observation/Remark
1.	Yes	100	Online Opting System
2.	Yes	83	Activity has effectively driven the student to self-learning.
3.	Yes	91	Many students were satisfied with the material and the way the faculty presented every topic in a form of a PPT. Students are happy with the relevant and sufficient material.
4.	Yes	85	Every individual has started thinking differently.
5.	Yes	75	Planning for business with nominal investment
6.	Yes	80	An Overwhelming majority of the students indicated an improvement in their communication skills.
7.	Yes	85	The students felt that little change in thinking makes winners.
8.	Yes	80	Students felt that their workplaces are going to be friendly and productivity can be improved
9.	Yes	90	Teachers should spend more time explaining the concepts and its objectives to learn more about it.
10.	No	95	Guidance should be given with practical examples
11.	Yes	100	Every individual is responsible for social and economical issues.

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